

Accreditation and Quality Assurance in University of Cross River State, Nigeria

Ettah Ettah Omini^{1*}, Kingsley Ichazu², George Ugbome²

¹Department of Educational Management, University of Calabar, Calabar - Nigeria.

²Delta State College of Education, Agbor.

* Corresponding Author

Email: ominietha@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examined accreditation and quality assurance in Cross River State Universities. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The design was a correlation survey with a population of 1481 university academic staff out of which 444 was the sample used. The instrument for data collection was titled Programme Accreditation Exercise Scale with high levels of reliability. The research questions were answered with Pearson statistics. T-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses. It was found among others that the quality of an accredited programme depends on the level of funding of a university in Cross River State. It was also indicated that the quality of programme accreditation and physical facilities of the university has a high relationship. It was also revealed that programmes accreditation is positively related to staffing in Cross River State University. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that academic staff should be included in the team of those who ensure quality programmes in the university. Private sector partnerships should be encouraged to fund a programme to ensure the quality of the programme in the university. Independent agencies should be engaged to monitor the activities of accreditation teams to avoid bias.

Keywords: Accreditation, assurance, quality assurance, quality, university.

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Introduction

Economic and social development is increasingly driven by the advancement and application of knowledge. Education in general and tertiary education, in particular, is widely accepted as a major instrument for the construction of a knowledge-based economy and society. According to the revised National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013), tertiary education is the education given after secondary education in universities, colleges of education, polytechnic and monotechnics including those institutions offering correspondence courses. Accordingly, Section 8 of the National Policy on Education 2013 states that the goals of tertiary education are to:

- a. Contribute to national development through high-level relevant manpower training
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- b. Develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society.
- c. Develop the intellectual capability of an individual to understand and appreciate their local and external environment.
- d. Acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of society.
- e. Promote and encourage scholarship and community service.
- f. Forge and cement national unity and
- g. Promote national and international understanding.

Despite the immense benefits of tertiary education to the nation's building, as pointed out by the above goals, their achievement has remained a mirage. According to Olaleye (2012:580), higher education in Nigeria, like other systems of education, especially in developing countries is going through a series of challenges. Saint et al. (2003) also observed that the potential of higher education systems in developing countries to fulfil their responsibility is frequently thwarted by long-standing problems. These multi-faceted problems have inhibited goal attainment led due to drawbacks in developing and have created fear and doubt about the quality of tertiary education in Nigeria.

To formally enhance quality in university education, like in other developing nations in the world, Nigeria has adopted various methodologies such as quality assurance, accreditation and audit to address the question of quality in university education similar to those in western countries. Quality assurance is an umbrella concept for a host of activities that are designed to improve the quality input, process and output of university education. Quality assurance is not accreditation as some erroneously conceive. Accreditation is one of the activities in quality assurance. Quality assurance and accreditation in university education in Nigeria is seen as systematic management and assessment of procedures adopted by the government to monitor performance and to ensure the achievement of quality improvement.

Admittedly, accreditation is one of the mechanisms for judging the quality of university education and has been employed by several countries, and so quality assurance aims to give stakeholders confidence about the management of quality and the outcome achieved. According to Okojie (2008), accreditation of universities whether it is institutional or programme is a way of examining the state of the institution in relation to where it ought to be and it is a quality assurance process. This accreditation as one of the processes of examining institutional procedures for assessing quality and assessing its management for effective implementation of strategies for achieving stated objectives has been employed in several countries.

The regulatory body in the Federal Republic of Nigeria in charge of accreditation and quality assurance of university education is the National Universities Commission (NUC). It discharges its duties by monitoring the internal and external quality assurance mechanisms of the universities and by assessing the standards of their programmes and educational delivery through some processes. These include the establishment of infrastructure, personnel, teaching/learning facilities, setting of admission criteria to institutional programmes, laid down processes of establishing and monitoring programmes and their implementation, use of external

examiners and accreditation programmes. The commission is involved with virtually all aspects of university education in the country, from registration, accreditation, recruitment and admission to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) development and implementation. In the accomplishment of its mission, the commission collates analysis and publishes information relating to university education. Such information includes academic programmes taught in particular universities, approval status, year of establishment, level of degrees that are offered, accreditation status and carrying capacity of the programme. Therefore, there are high expectations of the impact of the NUC accreditation exercise on the quality assurance indices of Nigerian universities.

The conspicuous indices for quality assurance in universities as a result of accreditation include academic content, funding, physical facilities, staffing and library. In this study, the relationship between programmes accreditation, funding, physical facilities and staffing are considered. Onifade et al. (2007) submitted that one of the areas of improvement that is often targeted in university education is funding. Funding affects every aspect of the university system. It can be noted that adequate provision of the fund is sacrosanct to quality assurance practices, this is because adequate funding will enable the institution to provide adequate physical facilities and the right staff capacity.

Staffing is one of the components of the accreditation instrument. The vision of the Nigeria higher education system has the following expectations; to be relevant and responsive to the need of the society and adequate in quality with a well-motivated, highly skilled and qualified staff whose products are knowledgeable, technically competent and adequately prepared to a fulfilled life and for positive contribution, to the society. Oladipo et al. (2009) found that staff dominate in lessons and pose few open-ended questions. Group work that encourages discussion is rarely encountered and 100% of teachers used continuous assessment. Oliver (2001) posits that effective tertiary teaching and learning setting should support and encourage:

- a. High levels of students' activity and encouragement
- b. Forms of collaboration and cooperation among learners.
- c. Situations where learners are exposed to a variety of different perspectives
- d. Assessment forms an integral part of the learning process and is sensitive to the intended uses of the learning outside the classroom.

To maintain quality in higher education, there are bound to be assessments in the educational process and methods. One of such areas to be assessed is that of staffing, how adequate is the quality and quantity of the teaching staff needed for effective teaching and learning. According to NUC (2007), manual accreditation in the areas assessed during accreditation includes academic staff, non-academic staff, head of departments/disciplines/sub-discipline and staff development. The adequacy of the teaching staff determines the adequacy of the programme as the instructional goal and objectives are achieved only to the level of competence and vision of the teaching staff.

Physical facilities are among the components of accreditation instruments and a determinant of the quality in the teaching and learning process in the educational system – physical facilities in higher institutions involves the provision of buildings, classrooms, hostels, staff quarters, workshops, laboratories, ICT centres, libraries, health centres and sports facilities. The acute shortage of all types of learning facilities is glaring in most Nigerian universities. The available facilities are over-stretched and overused thereby causing a rapid decline in the state of the facilities. In addition, to the inadequate provision of facilities is the maintenance of the old facilities. Maintenance culture is lacking in the management of the old facilities in the universities. The inadequacy in the funding of Nigerian universities has a major influence on the provision of qualitative and quantitative information material, staff and other facilities to enhance effective teaching and learning. According to the NEEDS assessment of Nigeria public universities report, the FRN (2012) indicated that a combination of infrastructural and manpower challenges are responsible for the sharp decline in scholarship in Nigerian universities.

The report showed that physical facilities for teaching and learning in public universities are inadequate, dilapidated and overstretched. Laboratory and workshop equipment, as well as consumables, are either absent, inadequate or outdated. Kerosene stoves are being used as Bunsen burners in some laboratories, some engineering workshops operate under trees and in dilapidated sheds. Therefore, to build and enhance quality programmes offered in institutions of higher learning like universities, maintaining and providing quality education is a fundamental aspect of gaining and upholding credibility for its programmes. It is against this background that this study examines the relationship between accreditation and quality assurance at Cross River State University.

Statement of problem

In recent years, there is little evidence about the actual impact of programme accreditation, exercises on quality assurance indices in Cross River universities with consideration to funding, physical facilities and staffing. This is reflected in the production of poor-quality graduates that are available to fit into the global competitive jobs. The situation has shown that quality assurance in terms of accreditation in Cross River State has not been fully implemented. For instance, some lecturers have been teaching under poor conditions of service, inadequate teaching facilities, excessive workload and poor funding of the university on the part of the government. Although the government and university authorities on their part have tried to salvage the situation by employing qualified teachers, sets standards for research publications, create room for staff development programmes. This study, therefore, investigates if there is a relationship between accreditation and quality assurance at Cross River State University.

Purpose of the study

The study seeks to examine accreditation and quality assurance; specifically, the study sought to:

1. Establish the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and level of funding university in Cross River State.
2. Ascertain the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and physical facilities in Cross River State University.
3. Examine the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and staffing in Cross River State University.

Research questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and the level of funding university?
2. What is the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and physical facilities of the university?
3. What is the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and staffing of the university?

Methods

This study adopted the correlational research design. The population of the study is made up of 1, 481 academic staff in the two universities in Cross River State. The University of Calabar (Unical) having 1, 106 and 375 academic staff from the Cross River State University of Technology (CRUTECH). A sample of 444 academic staff was involved in the study using a stratified random sampling technique. The researcher made use of two rating scales as the research instruments titled "Programme Accreditation Exercise Scale (PAES) with 10 items and Quality Assurance Indicator Scale (QHIS) with 30 items. Draft copies of the scale were given to three experts from the field of education, measurement and evaluation and two experts from educational management for validation.

Cronbach Alpha statistics were used to determine the reliability of the rating scales with indexes of 0.82 and 0.78 for (PAES) and (QAIS) respectively. The researcher visited the schools involved to collect data for the study and also administered the instrument to the respondents and patiently waited for them to fill their responses and collected at given a 100% ratio rate. The research questions were considered with person "r" statistics. This was used to establish the significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the study. The hypotheses were tested using t-test significance of correlation at a $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between programme accreditation and the level of funding of universities in Cross River State. Table 1 shows the correlation coefficient between

programme accreditation and the level of funding of universities in Cross River State. The result of the analysis indicated that the sample size is 444 while the correlation coefficient is .500, the coefficient of determination is .336. This implies that there is a very high positive relationship between programme accreditation and the level of funding universities in Cross River State.

Table 1: Relationship between programme accreditation and level of funding university in Cross River State.

Variables	Accreditation	Funding
Accreditation person correlation	1	.580
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
r ²		.336
N	444	444
Funding person correlation	.580	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
r ²	.336	
N	444	444

Research question 2

What is the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and physical facilities in Cross River State University? Table 2 shows the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and physical facilities of Cross River State University. The result of the analysis indicated that the sample size is 444 while the correlation coefficient is .740, the coefficient of determination is .548. This implies that there is a high positive relationship between programme accreditation and physical facilities in Cross River State Universities.

Table 2: Correlation Coefficient between Programme Accreditation and Physical Facilities in Cross River State University

Variables	Accreditation	Physical facilities
Accreditation person correlation	1	.740
Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
r ²		.548
N	444	444
Physical facilities correlation	.740	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
r ²	.548	
N	444	444

Research question 3

What is the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and staffing in Cross River State Universities? Table 3 shows the correlation coefficient between programme accreditation and staffing in Cross River State Universities. The result of the analysis indicated that the sample size is 444 while the correlation coefficient is 720, the coefficient of determination is .221. This implies that there is a very high positive relationship between programme accreditation and staffing in Cross River State Universities.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient between Programme Accreditation and Staffing in Cross River State Universities

Variables	Accreditation	Staffing
Accreditation person correlation	1	.761
Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
r ²		.579
N	444	444
Staffing correlation	.761	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
r ²	.579	
N	444	444

Fig 1: Graph of the various variables

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study indicated that there is a very high positive relationship between programme accreditation and level of funding in Cross River State Universities. This implies that funding plays a crucial role in the quality assurance measure of universities. This is because adequate funding improves the quality of inputs in the school system, but less funding led to the inference indicating that there is a significant relationship between programme accreditation and level of funding in Cross River State Universities. This finding is in agreement with Nwaogu 2007, who stated that one of the areas of improvement that is often targeted in university education is funding. Funding affects every aspect of the university system.

This study revealed that there is a high positive relationship between programme accreditation and physical facilities in Cross River State Universities. This could be explained that programme accreditation in terms of provision and maintenance. This implies that it can be generalized that programme accreditation of universities in Cross River State influences the quality assurance index of physical facilities. In line with this finding of Onifade which revealed that there is a relationship between accreditation and resource input in the universities. Both contrarily, findings indicated that the impact of Vocational Education and Training (VET) in Nigeria has not been impressive because of ineffective quality assurance at all levels. These discrepancies among the findings would be explained by the fact that the studies were not carried using the same universities. This could explain the variation in the findings.

It was also revealed in this study that there is also a revelation of programme accreditation being related positively to staffing in Cross River State Universities. This implies that there is a great influence programme accreditation on recruitment and selection of staff in Cross River State Universities. This explains why universities always employ more academic staff before NWC visits them for accreditation. In line with this finding Oyekan (2013) found out that quality control measures exert great influence on the quality of graduates in Nigerian universities.

Conclusion

The role of higher education in economic and social development is very strategic and indispensable. The dwindling quality of education in Nigeria has become a perennial issue that required a pragmatic approach. Accreditation is possible if quality assurance and development are given deserved attention. Without quality assurance and development, accreditation of relevant courses in tertiary education in Nigeria will remain an elusive endeavour. Higher educations are likely to be downgraded to degree mill offerings if the current trend of the downslide is not checked. The urge to continue to approve new generation universities is flawed without adequate physical facilities. The existing institutions need desperate help from the government in checkmating the causes of the dwindling quality assurance in Nigeria higher institutions. Nigeria may no longer desire aspirations to be among to 20 world economic

development if Nigerian education continues to slide. Quality assurance is highly relevant to the nation's economic development that seeks to provide well-qualified graduates capable of meeting the global economy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. University management should be made to be part of the accreditation team to understand the need of ensuring quality programmes of our courses.
2. University management should partner with the private sector to sponsor programmes in advance for accreditation.
3. The national university commission should also engage independent agencies to monitor the activities of accreditation teams to avoid nepotism.

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